

1 EEG revisited - neuronal, glial, and network mechanisms 2 across scales

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43 **Abstract**

44 Electroencephalography (EEG) has been providing a window into human brain activity
45 for nearly a century, yet its interpretation often remains empirical rather than
46 mechanistic. This review revisits the cellular and biophysical foundations of EEG
47 through a modern perspective, integrating advances from neurophysiology,
48 computational modeling, and cellular neuroscience. We examine the fundamental
49 physics of EEG generation, from transmembrane currents and dipole formation to the
50 effects of volume conduction and spatial summation. EEG results from coordinated
51 cellular and network activity, reflecting the integrated contributions of excitatory and
52 inhibitory synaptic events, intrinsic conductances, and tissue geometry, with pyramidal
53 neurons acting as dominant generators, while interneurons play a role in
54 rhythmogenesis and oscillatory coupling. Expanding beyond traditional Berger
55 frequencies, we highlight the significance of high-frequency oscillations and the
56 underlying cellular and network mechanisms that generate the high-frequency
57 component of the EEG signal. Conversely, infra-slow fluctuations and direct current
58 shifts reveal the roles of glial networks, ionic homeostasis, and spreading
59 depolarizations in health and disease. Across these domains, EEG uniquely captures
60 neural activity from sub-millisecond events to long-term state changes spanning days
61 or years, offering unparalleled temporal range to study the human brain. Clinically, this
62 multiscale capacity underpins the emergence of EEG-based biomarkers for epilepsy,
63 psychiatric disorders, and disorders of consciousness, while guiding development of
64 closed-loop neuromodulation and precision medicine strategies. With technological
65 advances and the expanding field of machine learning, the role of EEG will continue to
66 expand as we will gain deeper insights into its underlying mechanisms, advancing EEG
67 from a descriptive to a predictive tool in neuroscience and neurology.

68 **Key points**

- EEG reflects the integrated outcome of transmembrane currents, dipole geometry, and large-scale neuronal synchronization.
- Pyramidal neurons dominate EEG generation, while interneurons, thalamus, and subcortical inputs modulate synchronization and oscillatory precision.
- High-frequency oscillations and infra-slow/DC shifts expand EEG beyond traditional frequency bands.
- Glial networks shape infra-slow and DC activity, highlighting non-neuronal contributions to EEG dynamics.

Glossary

69 **Dipole**

70 A dipole is formed when an electrical charge separates, typically during synaptic
71 activity. For example, an excitatory postsynaptic potential (EPSP) in the apical dendrite
72 of a pyramidal neuron draws positive charge inward, while compensatory outward
73 currents flow elsewhere on the cell. This creates a source–sink pair, or dipole, that
74 radiates an electric field into the surrounding tissue. When thousands of pyramidal
75 neurons are similarly aligned, their dipoles sum and become large enough to be
76 recorded on the scalp as EEG.

77 **Source and sink**

78 In electrophysiology, a sink is the location where positive ions enter the cells (e.g.,
79 during synaptic depolarization), while a source is where current exits to complete the
80 circuit. Source–sink patterns describe how current flows in the extracellular space
81 around neurons. They are key to current-source density (CSD) analysis, which maps
82 the laminar origin of EEG and LFP signals. Understanding sources and sinks helps link
83 synaptic inputs to macroscopic EEG waveforms.

84 **Extracellular current and electric field**

85 Whenever transmembrane currents flow into or out of neurons, compensating
86 extracellular currents redistribute ions in the surrounding medium. These extracellular
87 currents generate electric fields that spread through the conductive tissue of the brain.
88 The strength and detectability of the field depend on the geometry of the source,
89 synchrony across populations, and the conductivity of intervening tissue. EEG

90 electrodes capture these extracellular fields, which represent the summed outcome of
91 countless neuronal and glial processes.

92 **Volume conduction**

93 Volume conduction refers to the passive spread of electrical fields through biological
94 tissue. Brain gray matter, white matter, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), skull, and scalp each
95 have distinct conductivities and geometries, which shape how local neuronal activity is
96 seen at the scalp. This explains why EEG has relatively poor spatial resolution
97 compared to invasive methods, but also why distant, synchronous activity can
98 dominate the EEG trace. Volume conduction is both a strength (allowing non-invasive
99 monitoring) and a limitation (blurring local sources).

100 **Resistivity**

101 Resistivity describes how strongly a material opposes the flow of electrical current.
102 Brain tissue has relatively low resistivity, allowing currents to spread, whereas the skull
103 has high resistivity, which strongly attenuates signals. Differences in resistivity
104 between layers (brain, CSF, skull, scalp) create a “filter” that shapes the amplitude and
105 frequency content of the EEG at the scalp. Modeling resistivity is essential for accurate
106 source localization and forward modeling of EEG signals.

107 **Local field potential (LFP)**

108 LFPs are extracellular recordings from electrodes placed in or near brain tissue,
109 typically spanning a few hundred micrometers around the electrode tip. They reflect
110 the summed synaptic currents, dendritic activity, and slower membrane fluctuations of
111 nearby neurons rather than action potentials. LFPs thus represent a mesoscale signal,
112 bridging the gap between single-cell electrophysiology, macroscopic intracerebral, and
113 scalp EEG. Because they capture finer detail, LFPs are widely used in animal

114 experiments and brain–machine interface research. In humans, LFPs can be recorded
115 using intracerebral electrodes that combine traditional macroelectrode contacts with
116 microelectrode contacts

117 **Infra-Slow Fluctuations**

118 Infra-slow fluctuations are very slow components of EEG activity, typically below 0.1
119 Hz, extending down to 0.01 Hz or lower. They reflect long-timescale changes in
120 excitability, metabolism, or glial activity rather than fast neuronal firing. These slow
121 shifts can regulate the excitability of faster oscillations, effectively acting as modulators
122 of brain state. Infra-slow activity has been implicated in sleep regulation, seizure
123 susceptibility, and disorders of consciousness.

124 **Direct Current (DC) Potentials**

125 DC potentials are sustained shifts in the EEG baseline voltage lasting from seconds to
126 minutes or longer. They occur during events such as cortical spreading depolarization,
127 seizure onset, ischemia, or large-scale metabolic shifts. Recording DC signals requires
128 special non-polarizable electrodes (e.g., Ag/AgCl) and stable amplifiers, since
129 standard EEG setups filter them out. Clinically, DC recordings provide unique insights
130 into pathological processes that conventional EEG might miss.

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134 **1. Introduction**

135 The history of EEG began with Hans Berger's first recordings of human brain
136 electrical activity in the 1920s, revealing that the brain emits measurable rhythms that
137 change with states of consciousness ^{1,2}. For nearly a century, EEG has been central
138 to neuroscience, neurology, and psychiatry ³. However, despite its wide use, its
139 interpretation often relies on empirical associations rather than mechanistic insights.
140 This gap has persisted because EEG signals emerge from the complex interplay of
141 cellular, network, and anatomical factors operating across multiple spatial and
142 temporal scales. The modern convergence of advanced recording technologies,
143 computational models, and molecular tools now offers a unique opportunity to revisit
144 and update our understanding of the cellular basis of EEG.

145 This review aims to integrate classical biophysical principles with emerging
146 knowledge of how diverse cell types and network dynamics shape EEG signals. We
147 focus on bridging subcellular activity to macroscopic field recordings, with particular
148 attention to cell types, including pyramidal neurons, interneurons and glia. Special
149 sections are devoted to the fast and slow components of EEG, including high-
150 frequency oscillations (HFOs), infra-slow fluctuations, and DC shifts, which are EEG
151 domains increasingly recognized for their clinical and mechanistic significance.

152 It is important to note that EEG is an epiphenomenon of cellular and network
153 activity. It reflects the collective outcome of transmembrane currents, synaptic
154 integration, and large-scale neuronal synchronization that underlie both normal
155 cognitive processes, such as perception, attention, and memory, and pathological
156 brain states. Altered oscillatory dynamics and abnormal rhythmogenesis are hallmarks
157 of many neurological and psychiatric disorders, including epilepsy, schizophrenia,

158 depression, intellectual disability, and Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases⁴⁻⁸. In
159 epilepsy, entirely new pathological patterns emerge in the form of pathological
160 oscillations and epileptiform discharges, where the breakdown of physiological
161 synchrony leads to excessively synchronous network activity⁹⁻¹². Thus, EEG provides
162 a unique macroscopic window onto the cellular and circuit-level mechanisms that
163 govern both normal cognition and disease. Furthermore, we highlight the unparalleled
164 range of time scales on which brain activity can be studied using EEG: from sub-
165 millisecond phenomena to processes spanning days, weeks, or years¹³⁻¹⁶.

166

167 **2. Physical, cellular, and network principles of EEG**

168 **2.1. Field generation at the membrane level**

169 Neuronal processing involves transmembrane ionic currents that generate
170 intracellular depolarizations or hyperpolarizations. Since transmembrane currents are
171 localized to specific cellular compartments, they generate both intracellular and
172 extracellular currents. The extracellular currents over non-zero resistance of the
173 extracellular milieu result in voltages known as local field potentials (Figure 1). For the
174 EEG, the most important events generating such currents are excitatory and inhibitory
175 postsynaptic potentials (EPSPs and IPSPs) on the membrane of the pyramidal
176 neurons which generate a dipole^{17,18}. In large, geometrically aligned cells, such as
177 cortical pyramidal neurons, these dipoles can sum up and become measurable by
178 macroscopic electrodes. Thus, these dipoles, resulting from EPSPs and IPSPs
179 occurring in the dendrites of cortical pyramidal cells, are the primary generators of the
180 local field potentials (LFPs) or EEG signal¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

181

182 **2.2. Pyramidal neurons as primary generators of the EEG signal**

183 Pyramidal neurons are the principal contributors to EEG signals owing to their
184 distinctive morphology, orientation, and integrative properties. Cortical structures have
185 an open-field configuration ²⁰, with pyramidal cells characterised by a long apical
186 dendrite ascending toward the pial surface and a basal dendritic tree extending around
187 the soma. When populations of pyramidal neurons receive synchronized synaptic
188 input, their aligned dendritic trees and spatially segregated input zones produce strong,
189 coherent extracellular dipoles ¹⁸. The consistent perpendicular orientation of these cells
190 relative to the cortical surface, combined with the lack of consistent orientation of
191 dendrites in non-perpendicular directions, makes them particularly effective in
192 generating summated laminar fields detectable by both surface EEG and intracranial
193 recordings (Figure 2A-C).

194 The contribution of pyramidal neurons to EEG activity depends critically on the
195 spatial distribution of synaptic inputs as well as the degree of temporal alignment
196 across neighboring neurons. Long-range corticocortical and thalamocortical excitatory
197 projections often target distal apical dendrites, while perisomatic regions integrate
198 inhibition ²¹⁻²³. This anatomical segregation enables the formation of dipolar fields, in
199 which excitatory and inhibitory currents summate in predictable spatial patterns.
200 Moreover, intrinsic axonal, somatic, and dendritic conductances further modulate the
201 temporal shaping of postsynaptic potentials ^{24,25}. Examples of these are dendritic h-
202 currents, low-threshold calcium spikes, persistent sodium currents, and slow
203 potassium conductances that prolong, amplify, or attenuate synaptic events or
204 generate after-hyperpolarizations, influencing both the amplitude and polarity of

205 extracellular field potentials ^{26–28}. Under pathological conditions, these mechanisms
206 can be amplified. For example in epilepsy, paroxysmal depolarization shifts and giant
207 excitatory postsynaptic potentials dominate the extracellular current flow, leading to
208 sharp, high-amplitude deflections that form the hallmark of interictal epileptiform
209 discharges ^{29,30}. Such events demonstrate how variations in intrinsic conductances and
210 network organization can scale up to shape the macroscopic morphology of EEG
211 waves across physiological and pathological brain states.

212 Beyond the contribution of excitatory postsynaptic potentials themselves,
213 several biophysical and network-level determinants shape the morphology and
214 detectability of EEG signals. The degree of synchrony across neuronal populations is
215 critical, since large numbers of pyramidal cells receiving temporally aligned inputs
216 generate large, coherent field potentials. In contrast, asynchronous synaptic input
217 prevents temporal summation of postsynaptic potentials. The distance from the source
218 to the electrode also determines amplitude (Figure 2B), with electric fields attenuating
219 as they propagate through brain tissue and skull, explaining why deep activity is
220 reduced at the scalp level. In addition, the distribution of synaptic input along the
221 dendritic tree plays a decisive role when distal apical inputs from thalamocortical or
222 corticocortical afferents produce field polarities distinct from proximal excitatory or
223 inhibitory inputs near the soma ³¹.

224 Computational modeling supports the essential role of pyramidal neurons in
225 EEG genesis by demonstrating that the geometry and alignment of pyramidal cells
226 maximize current summation and contribute considerably to the mesoscopic signal
227 ^{32,33}. Optogenetic studies further validate the central role of pyramidal neurons in
228 shaping cortical oscillations and event-related potentials ³⁴. Together, these findings

229 highlight pyramidal neurons as the dominant cellular generators of EEG signals, linking
230 single-cell physiology with the macroscopic rhythms recorded at the scalp.

231 In contrast to earlier views, it is now widely accepted that action potentials can
232 also contribute to the generation of EEG signals. A recent and elegant computational
233 modeling study utilizing spatially realistic models of neurons suggests that action
234 potentials may contribute up to 20% of the scalp EEG signal strength in frequencies
235 above the gamma band, but not to low-frequency components^{35,36}. More prominently,
236 synchronized action potential activity is observable in the EEG during evoked
237 potentials or pathological states, such as high-frequency oscillations or seizures, which
238 are discussed in detail below.

239

240 **2.3. Inhibitory neurons and network activity modulation**

241 Although pyramidal neurons dominate the generation of EEG signals due to
242 their geometry and abundance, inhibitory interneurons play a fundamental role in
243 shaping the temporal precision, synchronization, and coherence of cortical and
244 hippocampal network activity. These GABAergic neurons are extraordinarily diverse,
245 encompassing subtypes such as parvalbumin (PV)-positive basket and chandelier
246 cells, somatostatin (SST)-positive dendrite-targeting cells, and vasoactive intestinal
247 peptide (VIP)-expressing interneurons that preferentially inhibit other interneurons by
248 which they disinhibit pyramidal cells³⁷. Each class exerts distinct influences on
249 pyramidal cell excitability and oscillatory dynamics, either directly through inhibitory
250 postsynaptic potentials or indirectly by orchestrating excitation–inhibition balance
251 across circuits^{38,39}.

252 PV-positive fast-spiking interneurons are particularly critical for the generation
253 of gamma oscillations (30–100 Hz). By providing rhythmic perisomatic inhibition to
254 pyramidal neurons, they create synchronized inhibitory windows that structure
255 population firing, a process termed the pyramidal-interneuron network gamma (PING)
256 mechanism^{40,41}. This reciprocal interaction between pyramidal cells and interneurons
257 entrains the local network into rhythmic activity, with gamma frequency determined by
258 conduction and synaptic delays^{42,43}. An alternative model highlights interneuron–
259 interneuron (I–I) interactions, in which recurrent inhibitory coupling alone can sustain
260 gamma rhythms, with the decay constant of GABAergic currents setting the oscillation
261 frequency in local field potentials^{42,44}. Experimental and modeling studies suggest that
262 both mechanisms contribute to the generation of rhythmic activity, with relative
263 importance varying across brain regions⁴⁵. From the perspective of EEG genesis,
264 while the interneuron network provides timing for the oscillations, the EEG is generated
265 by the rhythmic IPSPs and EPSPs on the membrane of principal cells driven by the
266 inhibitory network. Cortical oscillations are closely linked to cognitive processes,
267 including attention, sensory integration, and working memory. Loss of interneurons,
268 alterations in their intrinsic properties, or disruptions to their coordinated activity can
269 profoundly impair the generation of network rhythms and their disruption has been
270 reported in schizophrenia, autism, Alzheimer’s disease, and epilepsy^{8,46–48}.

271 Other interneuron subtypes shape slower rhythms and long-range synchrony.
272 SST-positive dendrite-targeting interneurons regulate the distal excitability of
273 pyramidal neurons and contribute to theta and alpha oscillations⁴⁹. VIP-positive
274 interneurons act in a disinhibitory fashion by suppressing SST cells, dynamically
275 modulating excitatory flow during behaviorally relevant states⁵⁰. Interneurons can also
276 generate inhibitory field potentials themselves, although these signals are generally

277 weaker than pyramidal cell contributions. However, in specific cases, interneurons
278 directly shape identifiable EEG events, such as hilar interneurons participating in
279 dentate spikes⁵¹, or ripple-cycle inhibition sculpting hippocampal sharp-wave ripples
280⁵².

281 Sharp-wave ripples (SWRs), transient physiological high-frequency events
282 superimposed on sharp waves in the hippocampus, exemplify how inhibition shapes
283 temporally precise population activity. SWRs arise in CA1 from excitatory drive
284 originating in CA3 and are tightly locked to the firing of local interneurons^{53,54}.
285 Intracellular recordings demonstrate that the ripple oscillation largely reflects rhythmic
286 inhibitory postsynaptic potentials on CA1 pyramidal cells⁵². The tight synchrony
287 between interneuron activity and ripple cycles allows pyramidal neurons to fire in brief
288 windows, forming population spikes that encode sequential activity patterns associated
289 with memory formation. Replay of these sequences during sleep SWRs has been
290 demonstrated in rodents⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷ and is thought to support memory consolidation by
291 propagating hippocampal activity patterns to cortical regions. It is well documented that
292 perturbations of SWRs impair memory performance^{4,5}. In epilepsy, interictal
293 discharges display analogous effects and disrupt ripple-associated replay, leading to
294 memory deficits⁵⁸.

295 Beyond rhythmogenesis, interneurons play a crucial role in higher-order
296 coordination. By regulating the timing of pyramidal cell activity, interneurons promote
297 cross-frequency coupling, phase locking, and long-range coherence, thereby enabling
298 distributed networks to communicate effectively⁵⁹. EEG thus captures not only the
299 direct inhibitory contributions to extracellular fields but also the indirect modulatory
300 roles of interneurons in orchestrating the dynamics of excitatory populations, both
301 locally and over long distances. Pathological alterations in inhibitory function are

302 reflected in the EEG as the loss of physiological oscillations or the emergence of
303 abnormal rhythms. For example, reductions in gamma power or coherence have been
304 reported in schizophrenia and autism, intellectual disability linking interneuron
305 dysfunction to impaired cognition ⁶⁰. This includes a breakdown of cross-frequency
306 coupling—normally essential for coordinating information processing across temporal
307 scales—as well as weakened long-range coupling between distant brain regions.

308 EEG studies evaluating functional or effective connectivity in various
309 neurological and psychiatric conditions elegantly demonstrate network reorganization
310 due to deficits in local and global coupling. Impaired gamma oscillations have been
311 linked to cognitive and perceptual deficits in schizophrenia ⁶⁰. Reduced interneuron-
312 mediated synchrony contributes to memory decline in Alzheimer's disease ⁶¹.
313 Abnormal beta and gamma rhythms have been observed in Parkinson's disease,
314 affecting motor and cognitive function ⁶². The consequences of these network-level
315 alterations include the emergence of pathological oscillations and the loss of
316 physiological oscillatory patterns that support cognition.

317 In epilepsy, interneuron dysfunction acquires a particularly disruptive role. The
318 loss or failure of inhibitory control can give rise to synchronous discharges and
319 pathological rhythms, which manifest as interictal epileptiform discharges with rich
320 morphologies ranging from interictal spikes and spike-and-wave discharges to
321 polyspikes, epileptic bursts, and seizures ^{63,64}. These events are not merely
322 epiphenomena, as they reflect the presence of epileptic neurons and pathological
323 neuronal dynamics within the epileptic network, which has undergone structural and
324 functional reorganization. The roles of interneurons in epilepsy are far more complex
325 and beyond the scope of this review ⁶⁵. Several forms of interictal discharges are
326 directly due to the activity of interneurons, and excessive interneuronal activity is one

327 of the mechanisms responsible for seizure initiation^{65–69}. In addition, epileptiform
328 activity can interfere with physiological rhythms that support cognition, such as
329 hippocampal theta waves and cortical gamma oscillations. The functional interference
330 represents one of the mechanisms that can contribute to what epilepsy patients often
331 exhibit: comorbid cognitive impairments, including memory decline, attentional deficits,
332 and, in severe pediatric epilepsies, developmental arrest or regression^{70,71}. Thus,
333 interneuron dysfunction in epilepsy links the microscopic failure of inhibitory circuits to
334 the macroscopic signatures of abnormal epileptiform EEG activity and to the clinical
335 manifestations characterized by seizures and epilepsy-related cognitive comorbidities.

336 These observations highlight the utility of EEG in capturing oscillatory
337 alterations, making it a powerful tool for studying interneuron-mediated network
338 function in both healthy and diseased states. In summary, inhibitory interneurons
339 contribute to EEG signals primarily by shaping pyramidal cell activity. They are
340 indispensable for the generation and modulation of neural oscillations across a wide
341 frequency spectrum, ranging from theta to gamma to ripples, and for the temporal
342 coordination that underlies cognition. EEG, by tracking these oscillatory signatures and
343 their disruptions, offers unique insight into the dynamics of inhibition, rhythmogenesis,
344 and cognitive function in health and pathology.

345

346 **2.4. Multi-scale resolution of EEG**

347 One of the remarkable features of EEG is its capacity to resolve neural
348 processes across a wide range of spatial and temporal scales (Figure 3). On the spatial
349 axis, modern EEG systems, especially those utilizing high-density arrays or source
350 localization algorithms, can localize activity with resolutions ranging from several

351 centimeters to a few millimeters, particularly when combined with structural MRI or
352 conductivity models. More invasive techniques, such as
353 stereoelectroencephalography (SEEG) using microwires, enable submillimeter
354 precision, providing access to the dynamics of individual cortical layers and deep
355 structures. Temporally, EEG remains unparalleled³. It can track electrical activity with
356 sub-millisecond resolution, capturing fast oscillations such as gamma and high-
357 frequency bursts, as well as epileptiform discharges. Simultaneously, it can monitor
358 slow dynamics over minutes to hours, days, and even weeks, including state
359 transitions, circadian rhythms, and developmental changes in brain excitability^{15,72}.
360 The ability to continuously monitor brain activity over long durations allows researchers
361 to explore not only acute neural events but also plastic changes, pathological
362 progression, or treatment effects^{73,74}. Devices implanted into the brain or sub-scalp
363 electrodes can record EEG activity for months or years. These recording techniques
364 provide reliable information about the long-term dynamics of seizure and interictal
365 epileptiform activity and could help in the analysis of epilepsy cycles to monitor disease
366 activity or forecast the risk of seizure occurrence^{13,15}.

367

368 **3. EEG beyond traditional Berger's frequencies**

369 **3.1. High-Frequency Oscillations and Pathological Discharges**

370 High-frequency oscillations (HFOs), generally defined as activity above 80 Hz,
371 have emerged over the past decades as markers of neuronal network dynamics in both
372 physiological and pathological contexts. Within this frequency range, ripples (80–200
373 Hz) are most often associated with hippocampal-dependent memory consolidation and
374 replay during sleep^{53,75}, and are also frequent in epileptic tissue; fast ripples (>250 Hz)

375 are frequently observed in epileptic tissue and are considered a hallmark of
376 pathological synchrony in clusters of hyperexcitable neurons^{76,77}. HFOs thus represent
377 a unique phenomenon at the interface of single-neuron action potential firing and
378 mesoscopic LFP activity. As mentioned above, physiological ripple generation critically
379 depends on the interplay between excitatory pyramidal cells and inhibitory
380 interneurons, particularly parvalbumin-positive basket cells, which impose fast,
381 rhythmic inhibitory control^{52,78}. The result is a highly time-locked burst of pyramidal cell
382 activity, detectable in LFPs or intracerebral recordings.

383 The discovery of pathological HFOs raises questions about the physics and
384 neurophysiology of EEG genesis. Traditional theories assume that action potential
385 firing does not contribute to the EEG signal due to the short duration of action
386 potentials, which last only a few milliseconds^{12,14}. Recent computational studies
387 propose that action potentials can contribute to the physiological EEG^{35,36} and that
388 this contribution becomes more pronounced under epileptic conditions, when an
389 extremely high level of synchronized action-potential firing generates extracellular
390 electric fields strong enough to be detected in the EEG, manifesting as pathological
391 HFOs^{12,14}. Current theories assume that HFOs are generated by tightly synchronized
392 bursts of action potentials or by out-of-phase activity⁷⁹ of multiple neuronal populations
393 (clusters, aggregates) with highly synchronized action potential firing within each
394 population⁷⁸. HFOs and synchronous action potential firing, manifested as bursts of
395 population spikes, have long been recognized by experimental neurophysiologists
396 using wide-band recordings. However, their systematic detection in humans has
397 become feasible only after the implementation of clinical recording systems equipped
398 with wide-band capabilities and sufficiently high sampling rates.

399 Current models of epileptic ripple generation suggest that each ripple cycle
400 corresponds to a population spike, i.e., the field potential correlate of near-synchronous
401 action potential firing among principal cells ^{79–83}. Such synchronization occurs at
402 millisecond or even sub-millisecond timescales, necessitating rapid synchronizing
403 mechanisms. Candidate processes include fast synaptic transmission or non-synaptic
404 mechanisms such as gap-junction coupling ⁸⁴, ephaptic or field effect interactions ^{85–}
405 ⁸⁷. Suprathreshold excitation of pyramidal neurons initiates action potential firing, which
406 is subsequently phase-aligned by these mechanisms. Experimental and computational
407 work indicates that the firing rate of individual neurons strongly constrains ripple
408 frequency. Hippocampal CA3 pyramidal neurons, endowed with distinctive sodium,
409 potassium, and calcium channels and embedded within highly recurrent networks, are
410 predisposed to burst at rates near 200 Hz ⁸⁸. Under epileptic conditions, large
411 ensembles of CA3 neurons firing synchronously at this rate generate “pure” ripples
412 detectable in extracellular recordings. In chronic epileptic tissue, acquired
413 channelopathic and synaptopathic changes render principal neurons prone to high-
414 frequency bursting and paroxysmal depolarization shifts, thereby facilitating the
415 emergence of pathological ripple activity.

416 Interestingly, several in vitro and computational studies have shown that ripple-
417 like activity can arise even in the absence of extensive connectivity, simply from
418 coincident firing of a small group of highly active neurons ^{83,89}. The superposition of
419 action potentials from neurons firing at similar frequencies can summate into ripple-
420 band activity, even if precise phase alignment is lacking. Thus, ripple oscillations or
421 ripple activity may sometimes represent a marker of population excitability rather than
422 a coherent oscillatory state. Indeed, in low-calcium or high-potassium seizure models,
423 intense neuronal firing manifests in extracellular recordings as ripple-band high-

424 frequency activity without a fully formed oscillatory structure ^{90,91}. Compared with
425 physiological ripples, the role of interneurons in pathological ripple generation is less
426 clearly defined. Distinct interneuron subtypes contribute differently to excitability. For
427 example, somatostatin-positive interneurons regulate dendritic excitability ⁹², and their
428 loss enhances epileptogenicity, whereas perisomatic inhibition may be paradoxically
429 enhanced ⁹³. During interictal discharges, interneuronal dynamics are complex; while
430 dendritic interneurons and cholecystokinin-positive basket cells may increase their
431 firing, parvalbumin-positive interneurons often undergo depolarization block, disrupting
432 perisomatic inhibition ⁹⁴. Experiments in CA3 slices with fluorescently labeled
433 interneurons have shown that during pathological ripple-like events, a substantial
434 fraction of interneurons remain active on a cycle-by-cycle basis, suggesting that
435 inhibitory control is preserved locally and may still sculpt narrow time windows that
436 promote synchronous bursts of principal cell activity ⁹⁴. Thus, even pathological ripples
437 may represent bursts of population spikes orchestrated by altered, but not absent,
438 inhibitory control.

439 Fast ripples have garnered particular attention due to their apparent specificity
440 to epileptic tissue and their strong correlation with seizure onset zones. Their
441 mechanistic basis, however, has proven difficult to establish ¹². A key paradox is that
442 individual pyramidal neurons, even in epileptic tissue, cannot sustain firing rates high
443 enough (>300 Hz) to account for the frequencies observed in extracellular fast ripples,
444 which can reach up to 600 Hz ^{79,95}. The prevailing explanation is that fast ripples are
445 emergent network phenomena resulting from the interaction of multiple neuronal
446 subpopulations ^{79,90,95,96}. Within each subpopulation, neurons fire synchronously at
447 ripple-range frequencies, but slight phase delays between these subpopulations lead
448 to interference patterns detectable as higher-frequency activity in extracellular

449 recordings. Experimental and computational studies have implicated several
450 mechanisms in generating such out-of-phase activation: reduced spike-timing
451 variability⁸⁰, uncorrelated firing, neuronal loss⁹⁷, axonal sprouting and reorganization
452 promoting clustering⁹⁸, and delayed activation due to heterogeneous axonal
453 conduction times^{99,100}. The contribution of inhibition to the generation of fast ripples
454 remains debated. While inhibition is clearly essential for ripple formation, modeling
455 studies argue that inhibitory postsynaptic potentials cannot sustain oscillations above
456 ~250 Hz. Nevertheless, reducing GABAergic input or shifting the excitatory–inhibitory
457 balance toward NMDA-mediated excitation increases the likelihood of ripple-to-fast
458 ripple transitions^{82,89}.

459 More recently, fast ripples have been found to occur in mouse models of
460 Alzheimer’s disease (AD), exhibiting a striking resemblance to temporal lobe epilepsy
461 fast ripples¹⁰¹. Fast ripples in AD models primarily occurred within the hippocampal
462 dentate gyrus, a typically silent area of the hippocampus. They emerged before robust
463 AD-related neuropathology developed and well before the onset of cognitive decline.
464 Overall, HFOs within the fast ripple domain may have broader value in identifying
465 hyperexcitable circuits beyond epilepsy.

466 Clinically, HFOs have become valuable biomarkers of the epileptogenic zone,
467 offering predictive power for surgical outcomes beyond traditional interictal spike
468 mapping^{102–104}. Although recent trials have challenged their predictive validity in
469 temporal lobe epilepsy, they have shown promise for extratemporal epilepsy¹⁰⁵.
470 Technological advances, ranging from high-density microelectrode arrays to
471 automated machine learning–based detection algorithms, are expanding our ability to
472 detect, classify, and interpret HFOs across various scales. Moreover, the use of
473 standardized guidelines for recording, defining, and reporting HFOs is predicted to

474 enhance their utility in animal models ¹⁰⁶. Incorporating HFO analysis into EEG thus
475 expands the accessible frequency range of brain activity and deepens our mechanistic
476 understanding of how neuronal populations generate both normal and pathological
477 high-frequency activity.

478

479 **3.2. Infra-Slow Fluctuations, DC Recordings, and Glial Contributions**

480 EEG is often associated with oscillations in the classical Berger frequency bands (delta
481 through gamma), but it also captures activity at much slower time scales. Infra-slow
482 fluctuations (ISFs; <0.1 Hz), also known as direct current (DC) potential shifts ¹⁰⁷,
483 represent fundamental, though often overlooked, components of brain
484 electrophysiology. These slow signals are not simply low-frequency noise; they reflect
485 meaningful physiological processes spanning ionic regulation, metabolic state,
486 vascular coupling, and glial-neuronal interactions ^{108,109}. DC recordings, achieved with
487 stable, non-polarizable electrodes, enable detection of sustained voltage shifts that last
488 seconds to minutes or longer. A canonical example is cortical spreading depolarization,
489 in which massive neuronal and glial depolarization drives a large negative DC shift.
490 These events are associated with the redistribution of extracellular potassium, sodium,
491 and calcium, suppression of transmembrane ion gradients, and the transient failure of
492 the Na⁺/K⁺ pump ^{110,111}. Furthermore, DC shifts have also been observed during
493 physiological activities such as sleep ^{112,113}, cognitive tasks ^{113,114}, water intake ¹¹⁵,
494 motor activities ^{116,117}, hyperventilation ¹¹⁸, noninvasive changes in brain
495 hemodynamics ¹¹⁹ or chemotherapy-related blood-brain barrier disruption ¹²⁰. In clinical
496 contexts, DC potential changes can be observed in scalp EEG recordings during

497 seizure ^{121–124}, hypoxia and hyper- or hypocapnia ¹²⁵, ischemia ^{126–128}, migraine aura
498 ¹²⁹ and traumatic brain injury ¹³⁰, underscoring their translational importance ¹³¹.

499 The DC shifts can be generated by both neuronal and non-neuronal (e.g. glial)
500 mechanisms ^{107,118,132}. Astrocytes play a critical role in shaping infra-slow and DC
501 potentials through their ability to buffer extracellular potassium, uptake
502 neurotransmitters, regulate pH, and propagate calcium waves across large distances
503 ¹³³. Because astrocytic calcium transients occur on the order of seconds to minutes,
504 their influence is preferentially expressed in the slow components of the EEG. Calcium
505 waves spreading through astrocytic networks can couple to neuronal excitability by
506 modulating extracellular potassium and glutamate levels, thereby producing correlated
507 shifts in infra-slow EEG activity. Microglia and oligodendrocytes may also contribute,
508 particularly in pathological states where inflammation or demyelination alters ionic
509 homeostasis and leads to long-lasting changes in baseline potentials ¹³⁴

510 The biophysics of DC shifts emphasizes that they are not merely the result of
511 isolated neuronal activity but instead reflect sustained or synchronous activation of
512 EPSPs across cortical pyramidal populations, leading to large-scale sink-source
513 patterns. These patterns cause the extracellular potential to drift over time, forming the
514 biophysical substrate for slow field potential shifts and DC components in EEG
515 recordings. Negative DC deflections typically occur when sustained inward currents,
516 such as sodium and calcium influx, are present during depolarization. Conversely,
517 outward potassium currents, particularly during massive after-hyperpolarizations, can
518 shape repolarizing components of the DC signal ^{107,135}. At the network level, the
519 geometry of current sources and sinks plays a decisive role: open-field configurations
520 amplify the measurable DC shift, whereas closed-field geometries tend to cancel it.

521 In certain experimental conditions, particularly during CO₂/pH manipulations
522 and metabolic alterations, neuronal and glial membrane potentials do not consistently
523 vary in a manner that predicts the observed DC shifts. Moreover, some of these DC
524 shifts are exceptionally large, often in the millivolt range, and are not explained solely
525 by cortical dipoles. Both classic and more recent studies suggest that these slow
526 potential changes, particularly those triggered by respiratory or pH fluctuations, are
527 primarily generated by volume currents driven by CO₂-dependent potential differences
528 between blood and cerebrospinal fluid, e.g., across the blood-brain barrier (BBB),
529 rather than by neuronal or glial dipoles ^{118,119,136–138}.

530 Under certain experimental conditions, particularly during seizures and
531 spreading depression ^{132,139}, the observed DC shifts likely represent a complex
532 phenomenon arising from the interactions of multiple underlying mechanisms
533 described above. However, the quantitative contribution of neuronal, glial, and
534 epithelial potential differences to different types of DC shifts is unclear. In the modeling
535 study by Sætra et al., the relative influences of neuronal and glial dipoles, as well as
536 extracellular diffusive currents, on the generation of slow potentials were examined ¹⁴⁰.
537 The model predicted that the three components were on the same order of magnitude,
538 hence, no single mechanism can fully account for the observed DC phenomena.

539 From a functional perspective, slow DC potential changes can act as a
540 modulatory scaffold for faster brain rhythms. By shifting the excitability baseline of large
541 neuronal populations, DC fluctuations modulate the amplitude and phase of faster
542 oscillations, effectively gating higher-frequency communication across brain networks
543 ¹⁴¹. In epilepsy, pre-ictal DC shifts have been proposed as predictive biomarkers of
544 seizure susceptibility and epileptogenic focus, reflecting a progressive destabilization
545 of ionic and metabolic homeostasis ^{142–144}. In contrast, in disorders of consciousness,

546 persistent infra-slow fluctuations may signal preserved large-scale network integrity,
547 even when higher-frequency rhythms are diminished ¹⁰⁹.

548 Despite their importance, DC and infra-slow components have long been
549 neglected in clinical EEG due to the technical demands of stable DC recording, which
550 requires non-polarizable electrodes and amplifiers capable of rejecting drift and offset
551 ¹¹⁸. Nevertheless, modern approaches integrating DC-capable EEG with optical
552 imaging, ion-sensitive electrodes, and computational modeling are revealing the
553 integrated glial-neuronal mechanisms underlying these slow brain rhythms. By
554 incorporating DC and infra-slow activity into mainstream EEG analysis, we move
555 toward a richer, more mechanistic understanding of brain states, bridging the scale
556 between cellular ionic dynamics, network organization, and macroscopic brain activity.
557 The significance of DC potentials in EEG analysis is further strengthened by recent
558 observations showing that clinically meaningful scalp-recorded ictal DC shifts can be
559 reliably detected even with a filter time constant of 2 seconds, making their routine
560 assessment feasible in standard clinical recordings ¹⁴⁵.

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4. Conclusions

562 This review has explored the cellular and biophysical foundations of EEG
563 signals through a modern, multiscale lens, emphasizing the integration of traditional
564 principles with contemporary insights from neurophysiology, glial biology, advanced
565 imaging, and computational modeling. Far from being a coarse or merely correlative
566 method, EEG is a powerful, temporally precise readout of distributed brain activity that
567 reflects not only fast synaptic and spiking dynamics but also slower regulatory
568 processes involving glia, neuromodulators, and long-term network plasticity. The

569 growing understanding of the cellular mechanisms underlying EEG has profound
570 implications for clinical practice and translational neuroscience. EEG has long served
571 as a cornerstone diagnostic tool in epilepsy, sleep disorders, coma, and various
572 encephalopathies. However, the new ability to interpret specific EEG features in terms
573 of defined cellular and synaptic mechanisms offers the potential to move from
574 descriptive to mechanistically guided diagnosis and therapy. By expanding the analysis
575 bandwidth to include HFOs and infra-slow components, the EEG can now probe
576 cellular and circuit-level processes that were previously inaccessible. The potential of
577 EEG extends beyond real-time monitoring to longitudinal tracking of disease
578 progression, treatment efficacy, and brain recovery. As analytical methods mature and
579 clinical translation accelerates, EEG is poised to serve as both a foundational research
580 tool and a dynamic clinical instrument that bridges molecular, cellular, and systems
581 neuroscience. Understanding the EEG at the biophysical and cellular levels will
582 ultimately lead to therapies that improve outcomes for individuals across the spectrum
583 of neurological and psychiatric conditions. Future EEG research must therefore not
584 only refine the descriptive use of EEG but also establish how specific patterns, whether
585 oscillatory activity, network synchrony, or pathological discharges, reflect the
586 underlying physiology or pathology of the brain.

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597 **Conflicts of interest**

598 CPL, JK, JGRJ, MdC, and PJ have no conflicts of interest related to the manuscript
599 topic.

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612 **Figures and figure legends**

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Figure1. Biophysics of a dipole around a neuron. A: Neocortical pyramidal neuron at rest. Note the cell membrane flanked by positive charges on the outer side and negative charges on the inner side. This is due to electrostatic forces attracting positive charges to the negatively charged cell (at resting membrane potential of around -65 mV) and vice versa. B: Excitatory synapse on the distal part of the apical dendrite is activated, which leads to the influx of positively charged ions into the dendrite, leaving behind the negatively charged ions in the extracellular space. This creates a positive deflection in a virtual intracellular electrode and a negative deflection in a virtual extracellular electrode close to the synapse, a phenomenon called excitatory postsynaptic potential (EPSP). The depolarization of the neuron (a shift in the inner environment to less negative values) decreases the electrical field that attracts ions to the cell membrane. The release of ions from the membrane generates a capacitive return current i_{return} , which can be recorded by the extracellular electrode located near the soma. The scalp electrode in this example is close to the synapse and records a negative deflection. C: Simplified electrical circuit where the synapse is modeled as a controlled source of current. Note that the word "source" here is meant in the context of circuit theory and not in the context of current source density (CSD) analysis. The synapse creates a CSD sink due to the inward direction of the current. Resistors model the conductances of the intracellular and extracellular space, and the capacitor models the cell membrane capacitance. V_{LFP} is the voltage drop over the extracellular resistance, and it is the difference between the two depicted traces. Note that positive deflection is drawn upward in this figure.

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Figure 2. Biophysics of the EEG. A: Synaptic activity and transmembrane currents represent the main source of the recorded EEG. Activation of an excitatory synapse in the apical branch of the dendritic tree of a pyramidal cell (red dot) leads to the flow of positive charges into the cell (inward negative current, active current sink). It behaves as a dipole, and the current flows intracellularly and exits through the membrane at the proximal branch of the dendritic tree (outward positive currents, passive sources) to close the loop. This current flow must follow Kirchhoff's law, where the current entering the circuit must be equal to the current leaving the circuit. B: The current flowing in the extracellular space follows the electric field (red dashed lines) and sets up an extracellular potential (black dashed lines show equipotential loci). C: If a large group of neurons is synchronously activated and generates EPSPs on their apical dendrites, the resulting electric potential is sufficiently large to be detected by a scalp electrode, in this case as a negative deflection. D: Geometric organization substantially impacts the resulting electric field. Extracellular currents generated by the opposite dipoles cancel each other out, and no signal will be detected at the scalp. E: Neurons in the sulcus are oriented parallel to the brain surface. The scalp electrode is facing the zero isopotential line, and no voltage change will be detected. F: Brain nuclei or structures with closed-field structure are also associated with minimal changes in extracellular potential due to net charge cancellation outside the structure.

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Figure 3. Spatiotemporal properties of EEG compared with other experimental and clinical techniques. A: Schematic comparison of commonly used neurophysiological and neuroimaging techniques in terms of their spatial and temporal resolution. EEG spans a broad temporal range, from milliseconds to years, and can monitor large-scale brain dynamics, similar to in vivo imaging approaches. Cellular and subcellular processes require higher-resolution methods such as patch-clamp recordings or modern optical techniques (e.g., calcium, voltage, or neurotransmitter indicators), which provide detailed insights at the single-cell level. B: An example of EEG versatility in capturing epileptic activity across multiple temporal and spatial scales. Phenomena detected range from millisecond cellular events (e.g., high-frequency oscillations, interictal discharges) to network-level dynamics (e.g., seizures, spreading depression) and even long-term disease processes (e.g., epileptogenesis, progression, remission). This wide-ranging applicability makes EEG a unique tool for studying both fast neuronal activity and slow pathological trajectories within the same framework.

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